

Results of analysis of speech by Federal Chancellor Angela Merkel at Stanford University in Palo Alto (California), 15 April 2010.

This corpus has 1 document with 3,563 total words and 1,034 unique word forms. Created about a minute ago.

Vocabulary Density: 0.290

Readability Index: 11.123

Average Words Per Sentence: 19.3

Most frequent words in the corpus:

- freedom (21); countries (19); security (17); states (15); great (14); crisis (14); united (13); global (13); today

Results of analysis of speech by Federal Chancellor Angela Merkel in London, 27 February 2014.

This corpus has 1 document with 3,938 total words and 1,022 unique word forms. Created about a minute ago.

Vocabulary Density: 0.260

Readability Index: 10.340

Average Words Per Sentence: 21.8

Most frequent words in the corpus:

- european (54); europe (35); union (26); united (25); world (20)

References

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3. Emergent Approaches within the New Digital History. Edited by Mats Fridlund, Mila Oiva & Petri Paju. Published by Helsinki University Press, 2020.
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5. Umarov S. Bilateral relations Republic of Uzbekistan and Germany // *Вестник КазНУ. Серия историческая*. – 2019. – Т. 94. – №. 3. – С. 21-27.
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